

Impact of Quarrying Activities at the Nkolbisson Quarrying District Yaounde, Cameroon on the Environment and Health of Locals

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Abstract: Quarry operations carried out without the respect of best practices have posed environmental challenges globally, in addition of being among the most-risky industry to work in due to high number of reported health hazards. In Cameroon, quarrying in the past few years has been on the increase due to an increase in the level of urbanization and subsequent increase in the demand for aggregate for construction purposes. For this study, both quantitative and qualitative research design was adopted, targeting 125 respondents. Sampling was done by visiting the community and the quarry site, explaining the aim of this study to the people and permitting them to choose whether or not to participate. During data collection, questionnaires were chosen as main data gathering tool and the collected data descriptively and inferentially. The findings of this study showed a significant relationship between quarrying operations and environmental degradation. In view of the acquired outcome, the investigation reasoned that environmental degradation at Nkolbisson was due to unregulated stone excavation and therefore recommends that strict enforcement of existing regulatory frameworks be undertaken on non – compliant quarrying operations.

Keywords: Quarry operations; Land degradation; Air pollution; Health hazard; Regulatory framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quarrying and open-cast mining, in particular, play a significant economic role for the entire world's economy [1]. An upsurge in the demand for stones related supplies such as gravel and sand give rise to the need of quarrying. Many stone mining companies use open cast method which involves drilling and use of explosives to extract rocks from the earth.

According to [2], workers, society and cultural heritage, the natural environment, and nearby communities are all negatively impacted by quarrying activities. Also, [3], describes explosives use in quarries as potentially dangerous to both humans and the environment. Only 20-30% of explosive energy is required to fragment the rocks and the remaining energy get wasted in form of vibrations and flying rocks [4]. The extent of response of humans and the environment on the significance of such vibrations including destructions of buildings was given by [5]. According to [6], four million deaths are reported annually from acute respiratory problems in developing countries, owing to aggravated environmental pollution emanating from quarrying, sand blasting and emission of dangerous chemicals.

High rate of urbanization in Yaounde, has led to an increase in the demand for industrial minerals such as sand and dimension stones for construction purposes thereby increasing stress on the environment. The geology of the Yaounde makes it vulnerable to quarrying activities as a result of the presence of large deposits of metamorphic rocks which can be extracted through quarrying in order to meet up the high demand for such materials. Though quarrying brings about some positive impacts to the economy through tax payment as well as to the community through employment opportunities, it should be mentioned that this activity is seen as an evil due to the enormous negative impacts generated. These negative impacts may include deforestation, soil erosion, water pollution, ecosystem destruction, land degradation, creation of pits which might later be filled by water (lakes), and generation of dust/noise by blasting operations as well as equipment, etc. In Cameroon several research work has been done by [7] and [8] on the environmental and health impacts of artisanal mining on the locals but no such work has been carried on the impacts of quarrying on both the environment and health. As a result, this study is focused on the evaluation of negative environmental and health impacts generated by quarrying activities at Nkolbisson quarrying district.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area was confined to the Nkolbisson quarrying district composed of one abandoned and two active quarries, the nearby residential area from the quarrying district were classified into two zones based on distance away from the quarry, ranging from less than 300m, and 500m – 1000m respectively. Direct field observations were carried out in quarrying sites in order to appreciate the degree of environmental impact generated in each site. Data collection from the field was done by the use of guided questionnaires, interviews and focus group discussions with key informants. A total of 100 questionnaires were administered in the quarrying district, 80 to the local community and 20 to quarry workers. The first household was randomly selected and the rest of the households were selected after every 5 household counts. This was to avoid collecting the same information at the nearest household neighbor. Apart from administering questionnaires, interviews and a number of focus group discussions were organized with the quarry workers and nearby residents. The data collected through questionnaires were sorted, decoded and classified into different variables before analysis. The data was then treated with the aid of Excel to obtain summarized figures and tables.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Land Status

In surveying quarrying upshots on land form, respondents contrasted the present scene appearance 4 to 7 years ago. Towards accomplishing a reasonable appraisal, this inquiry coordinated with respondents who had resided in the region for equivalent or more years. From **Fig. 1**, obviously there has been extreme scene changes in the precedent 4-7 years. Remarkably 70% reported vegetative scenery previously but had now transformed. 46% referred soil erosion as a typical phenomenon right now that contrasted with 20% in the last 4-7 years. By and large, the scene of Nkolbisson can be portrayed as rough and exposed as asserted by 28%, and 16%.

Land Pollution

During rock quarrying operations explosives are used to fragment rocks within a given rock mass. Optimal rock fragmentation requires proper calculations of Powder Factor, thus revealing the type and amount of explosive needed to fragment a given volume of rock. Land pollution resulting from quarry operations can be look upon as the deposition of rock fragments of different sizes on land, transported by high explosive energy during blasting operations. Continuous used of such high energy favours continual deposition of rock fragment on land, hence polluting land intended for agricultural use. From **Table 1**, 93% of respondents affirmed the deposition of flying rocks on land during blasting operations and 83% attested the falling of flying rocks on the roof of nearby residents during the same operation.

Air Pollution

Quarry dust often contaminate the encompassing air. In deciding the degree of contamination, the pollster displayed interrelated articulations to informants who were requested to illustrate their understanding of the pronouncement in **Table 2**. From **Table 2**, quarrying exercises produced the most elevated amount of dust recounted in the investigation by 93% of the respondents. The outcomes likewise demonstrated that concentration of dust was outstanding during blasting processes amid dry seasons. Other than blasting, 98% likewise named quarry trucks as dust producers; a sign that quarry administration barely attempts counteractive measures like consistent sprinkling of water on earth roads to settle dust. Majority of the respondent recognised that dust cause disturbance by settling on roof tops, dried items and plant leaves. This as indicated by 93% (**Table 3**) of respondent made crops to fail. 50% announce that dust influence visibility risking occurrence of accidents by bike riders as well as truck drivers. This finding verified with [9], who found that plant photosynthesis decreases because of condensed leaf area.

Effects of Air Pollution on Health

In view of the information that quarries produce noteworthy measure of dust, the study examined if there were any health ramifications. Gathered information was broken down and displayed as shown in the **Fig 2**. The acquired result demonstrated that 80%, 91%, 74%, and 79% of informant endure Cold, Sneezing, Eye Issues and Sore Throat difficulties in that order. In spite of the fact that the investigation did not set a component to find out how health disintegration among a few respondents was completely due to quarry dust, 90% who viewed themselves as to have already been healthy, as of now see their wellbeing as fair or poor. Just 10% saw no distinction in their wellbeing status previously and after presented to dusty environment. [10], confirmed that long term dust exposure causes heightened death of Chinese workers. Also, [2] ascribed respiratory inconveniency to microparticles. From **Fig. 3**, 40%, 45% and 15% of informants claimed to have poor, fair and unchanged health respectively after being exposed to quarry dust.

Seismic and Noise Ramification

To learn whether rock excavation in Nkolbisson kept vibrations at negligible levels, the study asked adjoining community members whether they had encountered any seismic impacts. The assembled field depictions evidently exhibited some houses developed splits accredited to seismic impacts (**Fig. 4**). Respondents also said they endure noise nuisance as an extra annoyance from quarry locals. In light of these discoveries it is presume that rock excavation in the locality cause tremors beyond desired limits. A comparative report by [11] in Nigeria uncovered that walls close to Ewekoro limestone quarry, were “Split and broken down”.

Figure 1: Previous and Current comparison of Landscape features

Figure 2: Effects of Air Pollution on Health

Figure 3: Health after Dust Exposure

Figure 4: Blasting Induced Seismic Effects

Table 1: Response from Informants on Land Pollution

Statement	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
Do fly rocks fall on your land during blasting operations?	93	93	7	7
Do fly rocks fall on your roofs during blasting operations?	83	83	17	17

Table 2: Response from Informants on Air Pollution

Statement	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Quarrying activities is the main source of dust in your village	93	93	7	7	0	0
Dust concentration in the atmosphere is highest during rock blasting	44	44	49	49	7	7
Dust is also generated from the unsurfaced road by vehicles transporting quarrying products.	98	98	2	2	0	0
Rainy and cold weather reduce the amount of dust in the air	94	94	6	6	0	0
Dry weather promote dust emission	97	97	3	3	0	0

Table 3: Response from Informants on Dust Nuisance

Statement	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
Does dust settle on your roofing sheet or clothing?	100	100	0	0
Are the leaves of your crops or plants in the area covered with dust?	100	100	0	0
Do crops or plants grow well when dust coat leaves?	93	93	7	7
Does dust prevent you from seeing things a distance away?	50	50	50	50

IV. CONCLUSION

The quality of the environment can affect human health either directly or indirectly. Poor health and life, as well as the absence of sustainable development are major factors resulting from environmental deterioration. This study was aimed at assessing the environmental and health impacts of rock quarrying at the Nkolbisson mining district. It highlighted the views of affected people through questionnaires and interviews. Majority of the respondents were not happy with environmental degradation, air/noise pollution, blast induced seismicity and general damage to the ecosystems. The study likewise found that there were adequate regulations on rock quarrying but laxity in authorization exists and rock excavation will soon be unsustainable if the present standard proceeds. The experts, for example Ministry of Mines, Industry and Technological Development (MINMIDT) in this manner must guarantee conformity to excavation guidelines and violators penalized appropriately. Nkolbisson scenery for the preceding 4 – 7 years as per this investigation was genuinely green and attractive. This transformed with the current increment in rock excavation to a degree that it is nowadays stony and uncovered making the soil vulnerable against extreme soil disintegration. Dominantly individuals employed and residing near rock excavation locals were discovered to regularly endure coughing, wheezing and eye issues. Confirmations existed of dust soiling cleaned garments outside, clogging plants and shiny autos or tables. In light of this investigation outcomes, dust produce from excavation practices is a disturbance as well as have health ramification on people.

The following recommendations were made to both the decision makers who are directly involved in the review of rock quarrying activities to make informed decisions when issuing licences and to quarry management considering the rate at which environmental protection principles are being violated: stern authorization and enactment of excavation rules by agencies, communities and Nongovernmental Organisation (NGOs) to evade ecological deterioration since restoration is an exceptionally costly practice. Rehabilitation can nevertheless be embraced on already relinquished locales that can possibly be transformed to parks or gulf course; effective legal framework, strict laws and legislature are important as MINMIDT with help of legal force and village leadership must impose heavy sanction on quarry companies that do violate environmental protection principles; all quarry owners must draft and submit an Environmental Management Plan (EMP) in advance to ensure that potential negative impacts of their mining projects are assessed and incorporated into development plan. This becomes a prerequisite to get a permit; all blasting operations should be done with proper calculation and consideration of powder factor, spacing and burden.

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